

On $I\alpha$ - Open Set in Ideal Topological Spaces

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to study separation axioms and compactness of $I\alpha$ - open set in ideal topological spaces, which was introduced by M.E. Abd El-Monsef, etc [1].

Keywords: $I\alpha$ - open set; $I\alpha$ - T_0 - space; $I\alpha$ - T_1 - space; $I\alpha$ - T_2 - space; $I\alpha$ - R - space; $I\alpha$ - N - space and $I\alpha$ - compact space.

1. Introduction

The subject of ideals in topological spaces has been studied by Kuratowski [3] and Vaidyanathaswamy [7]. An ideal I on a set X is a nonempty collection of subsets of X which satisfies: (1) $A \in I$ and $B \subset A$ implies $B \in I$ and (2) $A \in I, B \in A$ implies $A \cup B \in I$.

Given a topological space (X, τ) with ideal I on X and if $P(X)$ is the set of all subsets of X . A set operator $(\)^*: P(X) \rightarrow P(X)$, called a local function [3] of A with respect to τ and I , is defined as follows: for $A \subset X$, $A^*(I, \tau) = \{x \in X: A \cap U \notin I \text{ for every } U \in \tau(x)\}$, where $\tau(x) = \{U \in \tau: x \in U\}$. Kuratowski closure operator $cl^*(\)$ for the topology $\tau^*(I, \tau)$, called the $\star$ -topology and finer than τ , is defined by $cl^*(A) = A \cup A^*(I, \tau)$ [6]. When there is no chance for confusion we will simply write A^* for $A^*(I, \tau)$ and τ^* for $\tau^*(I, \tau)$. If I is an ideal on X then (X, τ, I) is called an ideal topological space.

In an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) , if $A \subset X$ then $int^*(A)$ will denote the interior of A in (X, τ^*) . The closed subsets of X in (X, τ^*) are called $\star$ - closed sets. A subset A of an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) is $\star$ - closed if and only if $A^* \subset A$ [2].

For any ideal topological space (X, τ, I) , the collection $\{V - J: V \in \tau \text{ and } J \in I\}$ is a basis for τ^* [2]. The elements of τ^* are called $\star$ - open sets. A subset A of an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) is said to be $\star$ - dense set if $cl^*(A) = X$. It is clear that, in an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) , if $A \subset B \subset X$ then $A^* \subset B^*$ and so $cl^*(A) \subset cl^*(B)$.

Recall that, if (X, τ, I) is an ideal topological space and A is a subset of X then (A, τ_A, I_A) , where τ_A is the relative topology on A and $I_A = \{A \cap J : J \in I\}$, is an ideal topological subspace.

Given a topological space (X, τ) . A subset A of a space X is said to be α - open set if $A \subset \text{int}(cl(\text{int}(A)))$. The family of all α - open subsets of a space (X, τ) forms a topology on X , called the α - topology on X and denoted by τ_α . It is finer than τ . If every nowhere dense set in a space (X, τ) is closed then $\tau_\alpha = \tau$ [5].

The concept of a set operator $()^{\alpha*} : P(X) \rightarrow P(X)$ was introduced by A. A. Nasef [4] in 1992 which is called an α - local function of I with respect to τ . It was defined as follows: for $A \subset X$, $A^{\alpha*}(I, \tau) = \{x \in X : A \cap U \notin I \text{ for every } U \in \tau_\alpha(x)\}$ where $\tau_\alpha(x) = \{U \in \tau_\alpha : x \in U\}$. When there is no chance for confusion we will simply write $A^{\alpha*}$ for $A^{\alpha*}(I, \tau)$. An α^* - closure operator, denoted by $cl^{\alpha*}()$, for a topology $\tau^{\alpha*}(I, \tau)$ which is called the α^* - topology, finer than τ . It is defined as follows: $cl^{\alpha*}(A)(I, \tau) = A \cup A^{\alpha*}(I, \tau)$. When there is no ambiguity we will simply write $cl^{\alpha*}(A)$ for $cl^{\alpha*}(A)(I, \tau)$. A basis $\mathfrak{B}(I, \tau)$ for $\tau^{\alpha*}$ is described as follows: $\mathfrak{B}(I, \tau) = \{V - J : V \in \tau_\alpha \text{ and } J \in I\}$. We will denote by $\text{int}^{\alpha*}(A)$ and $cl^{\alpha*}(A)$ the interior and closure of $A \subset (X, \tau, I)$ with respect to $\tau^{\alpha*}$. The elements of $\tau^{\alpha*}$ are called $\tau^{\alpha*}$ - open sets. Closed subsets of X in $(X, \tau^{\alpha*})$ are called $\tau^{\alpha*}$ - closed sets. A subset A of an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) is $\tau^{\alpha*}$ - closed (respectively, $\tau^{\alpha*}$ - dense) if and only if $A^{\alpha*} \subset A$ (respectively, $cl^{\alpha*}(A) = X$). In an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) if $A \subset B \subset X$ then $A^{\alpha*} \subset B^{\alpha*}$ and $cl^{\alpha*}(A) \subset cl^{\alpha*}(B)$. So $A^{\alpha*} \subset A^*$ and $cl^{\alpha*}(A) \subset cl^*(A)$.

Given a topological space (X, τ) . A subset A of X is said to be $I\alpha$ - open set if $A \subset \text{int}(cl^{\alpha*}(\text{int}(A)))$. The family of all $I\alpha$ - open subsets of a space (X, τ) is denoted by $I\alpha O(X)$ [1]. Consider the ideal topological spaces (X, τ, I) and (Y, σ, J) and define a function $f : (X, \tau, I) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, J)$ such that f is $I\alpha$ -irresolute homeomorphism, i.e..., then if the ideal topological space (X, τ, I) has any property P and the ideal topological space (Y, σ, J) has the same property P then P is called $I\alpha$ - topological property. A property P of an ideal topological space X is said to be $I\alpha$ - hereditary property if and only if every $I\alpha$ - subspace of X also possesses property P .

In the following subjects we need to remember some concepts introduced by Radwan in 2015 [6]. An $I\alpha$ - boundary set is defined as: Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space and $A \subseteq X$. $x \in X$ is said to be an $I\alpha$ - boundary point of A if for every $I\alpha$ - open neighborhood set for x satisfies that the intersection with A and A^c is nonempty set. The set of all $I\alpha$ - boundary points of A is called $I\alpha$ -boundary set of A and simply is denoted by $I\alpha - b(A)$. Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space and $A \subseteq X$. Then $I\alpha$ - closure set of A is defined by the union of A and $I\alpha$ -derived set of A and simply is denoted by $I\alpha - cl(A)$. Let $f : (X, \tau, I) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, J)$ be a function. f is said to be $I\alpha$ - irresolute function if the inverse image of every $J\alpha$ - open set in Y is $I\alpha$ - open set in X . $I\alpha$ - topological property is a new property which defined as Consider the ideal topological spaces (X, τ, I) and (Y, σ, J) such that $f : (X, \tau, I) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, J)$ is $I\alpha$ - irresolute function. Then if X satisfies any property P so did Y then this property is called $I\alpha$ - topological property.

2. SEPARATION AXIOMS IN $I\alpha$ - OPEN SETS

In this section, we will study some properties of different types of separation axioms on the level of ideal topological spaces using $I\alpha$ - open sets.

Definition 2.1 Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space then it is called $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - space if for any two different elements in X there exist an $I\alpha$ - open set in X containing one element of them but does not contain the other element.

Proposition 2.2 (X, τ, I) is an $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - space if and only if $I\alpha-cl(x) \neq I\alpha-cl(y)$ for any $x, y \in X$ such that $x \neq y$.

Remark 2.3 The $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - property is not hereditary property.

Example 2.4 Consider the ideal topological space (X, τ, I) such that $X = \{x, y, z\}, \tau = \mathcal{P}(X), I = \{\emptyset, \{y\}\}$ then $I\alpha O(X) = \mathcal{P}(X)$. It is clear that X is $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - space but if we take $w = \{x\} \subseteq X$, then (w, τ_w, I_w) is not $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - space for $I\alpha O(w) = \{w, \emptyset\}$.

Corollary 2.5 The $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - property is $I\alpha$ - hereditary property.

Remark 2.6 The continuous image of $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - space is not necessary to be $J\alpha-T_\sigma$ as the following example shows.

Example 2.7 Consider the ideal topological spaces (X, τ, I) and (X, τ, J) such that $X = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}, I = \mathcal{P}(X)$ and $J = \{\emptyset\}$.

Then $I\alpha O(X) = \tau$ and $J\alpha O(X) = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$.

Define a function $f: (X, \tau, I) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, J)$ such that $f(a) = f(b) = f(c) = f(d) = \{a\}$. Then $f^{-1}(X) = X \in I\alpha O(X), f^{-1}(\emptyset) = \emptyset \in I\alpha O(X)$ and

$f^{-1}\{a\} = f^{-1}\{a, b\} = f^{-1}\{a, c\} = f^{-1}\{a, c, d\} = f^{-1}\{a, b, d\} = X \in I\alpha O(X)$. Thus f is $I\alpha$ - continuous function and it is clear that (X, τ, J) is $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - space but (X, τ, I) is not $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - space for $c, d \in X$ such that $c \neq d$ the only $I\alpha$ - open set contains c is X but it is also contain d .

Remark 2.8 The $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - property is not necessary to be topological property, as the following example shows.

Example 2.9 Consider the ideal topological spaces (X, τ, I) and (X, τ, J) such that $X = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}, I = \mathcal{P}(X)$ and $J = \{\emptyset\}$.

Then $I\alpha O(X) = \tau$ and $J\alpha O(X) = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$.

Define a function $f: (X, \tau, I) \rightarrow (X, \tau, J)$ such that $f(x) = x, \forall x \in X$. Then (X, τ, J) is $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - space but (X, τ, I) is not because, if we take $c, d \in X$ such that $c \neq d$ the only $I\alpha$ - open set contains c is X but it is also contain d .

Corollary 2.10 The $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - property is $I\alpha$ - topological property.

Remark 2.11 Every T_σ - space is $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - space but the converse is not necessary to be true, as the following example shows.

Example 2.12 Take the ideal topological space (X, τ, I) such that $X = \{a, b, c, d\}, \tau = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$ and $I = \{\emptyset, \{b\}\}$. Then $I\alpha O(X) = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, c\},$

$\{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$.

From τ we get that the space X is not T_σ - space but from $I\alpha O(X)$ we get that the space is $I\alpha-T_\sigma$ - space.

Definition 2.13 Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space. Then it is called $I\alpha-T_1$ - space if for any two different elements in X there exist two $I\alpha$ - open sets in X such that each $I\alpha$ - open set of them containing only one element of those elements.

Proposition 2.14 (X, τ, I) is an $I\alpha$ - T_1 - space if and only if for any element x in X we have that $\{x\}$ are $I\alpha$ -closed sets in X .

Corollary 2.15 An ideal topological space (X, τ, I) is an $I\alpha$ - T_1 - space if and only if the following statements are equivalent:

- i. $I\alpha\text{-cl}\{x\} = \{x\}$, $\forall x \in X$.
- ii. $\{x\} = \cap \{F : F \in I\alpha C(X) \wedge x \in F\}$, $\forall x \in X$.
- iii. $I\alpha\text{-b}\{x\} \subseteq \{x\}$, $\forall x \in X$.
- iv. $I\alpha\text{-d}\{x\} \subseteq \{x\}$, $\forall x \in X$.
- v. $I\alpha\text{-d}\{x\} = \emptyset$, $\forall x \in X$.

Corollary 2.16 $I\alpha$ - T_1 - property is $I\alpha$ -hereditary property.

Remark 2.17 $I\alpha$ - T_1 - property is not topological property, as the following example shows.

Corollary 2.18 $I\alpha$ - T_1 - property is $I\alpha$ - topological property.

Remark 2.19 Every T_1 - space is $I\alpha$ - T_1 - space but the converse is not necessary to be true. As the following example shows:

Example 2.20 Consider the ideal topological space $(\mathcal{N}, \tau, I)$ where $\tau = \{u_n \subseteq \mathcal{N} : u_n = \{n, n + 1, \dots\}, n \in \mathcal{N}\} \cup \{\emptyset\}$ and $I = \{\emptyset\}$, then the family of all $I\alpha$ - open subsets of $\mathcal{N}$ is $\{A \cup u_n : A \subseteq \mathcal{N} \text{ and } u_n \in \tau - \{\emptyset\}\} \cup \{\emptyset\}$. It is clear that $(\mathcal{N}, \tau, I)$ is $I\alpha$ - T_1 - space which is not T_1 - space since, if we fix $x = 1$ then for any element $y \in \mathcal{N}$ there is no open set v containing 1 but not contains y .

Remark 2.21 Every $I\alpha$ - T_1 - space is $I\alpha$ - T_σ - space but the converse is not necessary to be true, as the following example shows.

Example 2.22 The (X, τ, I) in Example 2.12 is $I\alpha$ - T_σ - space but it is not $I\alpha$ - T_1 - space for $a, b \in X$ such that $a \neq b$ there is no two $I\alpha$ - open sets in X such that each $I\alpha$ - open set of them containing only one element of those elements.

Remark 2.23 $I\alpha$ - T_1 - property is not hereditary property.

Definition 2.24 Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space. It is called $I\alpha$ - T_2 - space if for any two different elements in X there exist two disjoint $I\alpha$ - open sets in X such that each $I\alpha$ - open set of them containing only one element of those elements.

Remark 2.25 $I\alpha$ - T_2 - property is not hereditary property.

Corollary 2.26 $I\alpha$ - T_2 - property is $I\alpha$ - hereditary property.

Remark 2.27 $I\alpha$ - T_2 - property is not topological property.

Corollary 2.28 $I\alpha$ - T_2 - property is $I\alpha$ - topological property.

Remark 2.29 Every T_2 - space is $I\alpha$ - T_2 - space but the converse is not necessary to be true.

Remark 2.30 Every $I\alpha$ - T_2 - space is $I\alpha$ - T_1 - space is $I\alpha$ - T_σ - space but the converse is not necessary to be true.

Example 2.31 The (X, τ, I) in Example 2.12 is $I\alpha$ - T_σ - space but it is not $I\alpha$ - T_2 - space for $a, b \in X$ such that $a \neq b$ there is no two disjoint $I\alpha$ - open sets in X such that each $I\alpha$ - open set of them containing only one

element of those elements. the ideal topological space in Example 2.21 is $I\alpha-T_1$ - space but not $I\alpha-T_2$ - space for any two $I\alpha$ - open sets in $\mathcal{N}$, the intersection of them is not empty set.

Definition 2.32 Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space. It is called $I\alpha$ - regular space if for every element in X and $I\alpha$ - closed set in X does not contain the previous element then there exist two disjoint $I\alpha$ - open sets in X such that one of them containing the element and the other set containing the $I\alpha$ - closed set. It is denoted by $I\alpha-R$ -space.

Definition 2.33 Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space. It is called almost $I\alpha$ - regular space if for every element in X and every closed set in X does not contain the previous element then there exist two disjoint $I\alpha$ - open sets in X such that one of them containing the element and the other set containing the closed set. It is denoted by almost- $I\alpha-R$ -space.

Proposition 2.34 (X, τ, I) is an $I\alpha-R$ - space if and only if for any element x in X and every $I\alpha$ - open set U in X such that $x \in U$ then there exists another $I\alpha$ - open set V in X satisfying that $x \in V \subseteq I\alpha-cl(V) \subseteq U$.

Proposition 2.35 (X, τ, I) is an almost $I\alpha-R$ - space if and only if for any element x in X and every open set U in X such that $x \in U$ then there exists another $I\alpha$ - open set V in X satisfying that $x \in V \subseteq I\alpha-cl(V) \subseteq U$.

Remark 2.36 Both $I\alpha-R$ - property and almost $I\alpha-R$ - property are not hereditary properties.

Corollary 2.37 $I\alpha-R$ - property is $I\alpha$ - hereditary property.

Remark 2.38 $I\alpha-R$ - property and almost $I\alpha-R$ - property are not topological property.

Corollary 2.39 $I\alpha-R$ - property is $I\alpha$ - topological property.

Remark 2.40 Every R - space is almost $I\alpha-R$ - space $I\alpha-R$ - space but the converse is not necessary to be true.

Definition 2.41 Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space then it is called $I\alpha-T_3$ -space if X is $I\alpha-T_1$ -space and $I\alpha-R$ -space.

Definition 2.42 Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space then it is called almost $I\alpha-T_3$ -space if X is $I\alpha-T_1$ - space and almost $I\alpha-R$ -space.

Proposition 2.43 If the ideal topological space (X, τ, I) is $I\alpha-T_3$ -space then (X, τ, I) is $I\alpha-T_2$ -space.

Corollary 2.44 Both almost $I\alpha-T_3$ - property and $I\alpha-T_3$ - property are not hereditary property.

Proof $I\alpha-R$ - property, almost $I\alpha-R$ - property and $I\alpha-T_1$ - property are not hereditary properties.

Corollary 2.54 $I\alpha-T_3$ - property is $I\alpha$ - hereditary property.

Proof Both $I\alpha-R$ - property and $I\alpha-T_1$ - property are $I\alpha$ - hereditary properties.

Corollary 2.46 Both almost $I\alpha-T_3$ - property and $I\alpha-T_3$ - property are not topological properties.

Proof $I\alpha-R$ - property, almost $I\alpha-R$ - property and $I\alpha-T_1$ - property are not topological properties.

Corollary 2.47 $I\alpha-T_3$ - property is $I\alpha$ - topological property.

Proof Both $I\alpha-R$ - property and $I\alpha-T_1$ - property are $I\alpha$ - topological properties.

Remark 2.48 Every T_3 - space is almost $I\alpha-T_3$ - space is $I\alpha-T_3$ - space but the converse is not necessary to be true.

Definition 2.49 Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space then it is called $I\alpha$ - normal space if for every two disjoint $I\alpha$ - closed sets in X there exist two disjoint $I\alpha$ - open sets in X such that each $I\alpha$ - open set contain only one of the two disjoint $I\alpha$ - closed sets in X . It is denoted by $I\alpha$ - N -space.

Definition 2.50 Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space then it is called almost $I\alpha$ - normal space if for every two disjoint closed sets in X there exist two disjoint $I\alpha$ - open sets in X such that each $I\alpha$ - open set contain only one of the two disjoint closed sets in X . It is denoted by almost $I\alpha$ - N -space.

Proposition 2.51 (X, τ, I) is an $I\alpha$ - N - space if and only if for any $I\alpha$ - closed set F in X and every $I\alpha$ - open set U in X containing F then there exists another $I\alpha$ - open set V in X satisfying that $F \subseteq V \subseteq I\alpha\text{-cl}(V) \subseteq U$.

Proposition 2.52 (X, τ, I) is almost $I\alpha$ - N - space if and only if for any closed set F in X and every open set U in X containing F then there exists another $I\alpha$ - open set V in X satisfying that $F \subseteq V \subseteq I\alpha\text{-cl}(V) \subseteq U$.

Remark 2.53 Both $I\alpha$ - N - property and almost $I\alpha$ - N - property are not hereditary properties.

Example 2.54 Consider the ideal topological space (X, τ, I) such that $X = \{1,2,3,4\}$, $\tau = \{X, \emptyset, \{2\}, \{1,2\}, \{2,3\}, \{1,2,3\}\}$ and $I = \mathcal{P}(X)$. Then $I\alpha O(X) = \tau$. It is clear that (X, τ, I) is $I\alpha$ - N - space and almost $I\alpha$ - N -space but if we take $A = \{1,2,3\} \subseteq X$ then (A, τ_A, I_A) is neither $I\alpha$ - N - space nor almost $I\alpha$ - N - space for $\tau_A = I\alpha O(A) = \{A, \emptyset, \{2\}, \{1,2\}, \{2,3\}\}$, then $\{1\}, \{3\} \in F_A = I\alpha C(A)$ such that $\{1\} \cap \{3\} = \emptyset$ and $\{1\} \subseteq \{1,2\} \in I\alpha O(A)$, $\{3\} \subseteq \{2,3\} \in I\alpha O(A)$ but $\{1,2\} \cap \{2,3\} \neq \emptyset$.

Corollary 2.55 $I\alpha$ - N - property is $I\alpha$ - hereditary property.

Remark 2.56 Both $I\alpha$ - N - property and almost $I\alpha$ - N - property are not topological property.

Corollary 2.57 $I\alpha$ - N - property is $I\alpha$ - topological property.

Remark 2.58 Every N - space is almost $I\alpha$ - N - space $I\alpha$ - N - space but the converse is not necessary to be true.

Definition 2.59 Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space. It is called $I\alpha$ - T_4 -space if X is $I\alpha$ - T_1 -space and $I\alpha$ - N -space.

Definition 2.60 Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space. It is called almost $I\alpha$ - T_4 -space if X is $I\alpha$ - T_1 -space and almost $I\alpha$ - N -space.

Proposition 2.61 Every $I\alpha$ - T_4 -space is $I\alpha$ - R -space.

Proposition 2.62 Every $I\alpha$ - T_4 -space is $I\alpha$ - T_3 -space.

Remark 2.63 Both almost $I\alpha$ - T_4 - property and $I\alpha$ - T_4 - property are not hereditary properties.

Proof $I\alpha$ - N - property, almost $I\alpha$ - N - property and $I\alpha$ - T_1 - property are not hereditary properties.

Corollary 2.64 $I\alpha$ - T_4 - property is $I\alpha$ - hereditary property.

Remark 2.65 Both almost $I\alpha$ - T_4 - property and $I\alpha$ - T_4 - property are not topological properties.

Proof $I\alpha$ - N - property, almost $I\alpha$ - N - property and $I\alpha$ - T_1 - property are not topological properties.

Corollary 2.66 $I\alpha$ - T_4 - property is $I\alpha$ - topological property.

Remark 2.67 Every T_4 - space is almost $I\alpha$ - T_4 - space is $I\alpha$ - T_4 - space but the converse is not necessary to be true.

3. $I\alpha$ - COMPACT SPACES

In this section we will study $I\alpha$ - compact spaces using the concept $I\alpha$ - open sets.

Definition 3.1 A subset A of an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) is said to be $I\alpha$ - compact if for every cover $\{u_\alpha: \alpha \in \Lambda\}$ by $I\alpha$ - open sets in X for A , there is a finite subfamily Λ_0 of Λ such that $A - \cup \{u_\alpha: \alpha \in \Lambda_0\} \in I$. A space (X, τ, I) is $I\alpha$ - compact if X is $I\alpha$ - compact as a set.

Remark 3.2 $I\alpha$ - compact property is not hereditary property.

Example 3.3 Consider the ideal topological space (X, τ, I) such that $X = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0, -1\}, \tau = \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N}) \cup \{H \subseteq \mathbb{N}: H^c \text{ is finite, } 0 \in H \text{ or } -1 \in H\}$ and $I = \{\emptyset\}$. Then $I\alpha O(X) = \tau$. The ideal topological space (X, τ, I) is an $I\alpha$ - compact space and by taking $A = \mathbb{N} \subseteq X$ which is not $I\alpha$ - compact space for: $\{\{n\}: n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is $I\alpha$ open cover for $\mathbb{N}$ but $\mathbb{N} - \cup \{1, 2, \dots, m\} = \text{infinite set} \notin I$.

Remark 3.4 $I\alpha$ - compact property is neither topological property nor $I\alpha$ - topological property.

Example 3.5 Consider the ideal topological spaces (X, τ, I) and (Y, σ, J) such that $X = Y = \mathbb{N}, \tau = \sigma = D, I = D$ and $J = \emptyset$. Then $I\alpha O(X) = I\alpha O(Y) = D$.

Define a function $f: (X, \tau, I) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma, J)$ such that $f(a) = a \forall a \in X$ thus f is continuous, 1-1, onto function and f^{-1} is also continuous. (X, τ, I) is $I\alpha$ - compact space but (Y, σ, J) is not. We can see that f is also $I\alpha$ - irresolute function and f^{-1} is $j\alpha$ - irresolute function. Hence $I\alpha$ - compact property is neither topological nor $I\alpha$ - topological property.

Corollary 3.6 If $A, B \subseteq X$ such that A, B are $I\alpha$ - compact sets over X then $A \cup B$ is also $I\alpha$ - compact set.

Remark 3.7 If $A, B \subseteq X$ such that A, B are $I\alpha$ - compact sets over X then it is not necessary that $A \cap B$ to be $I\alpha$ - compact set. As the following example shows.

Example 3.8 Consider the ideal topological space (X, τ, I) such that $X = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0, -1\}, \tau = \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N}) \cup \{H \subseteq \mathbb{N}: H^c \text{ is finite, } 0 \in H \text{ or } -1 \in H\}$ and $I = \{\emptyset\}$. Then $I\alpha O(X) = \tau$. The ideal topological space (X, τ, I) is an $I\alpha$ - compact space and by taking $A = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}, B = \mathbb{N} \cup \{-1\}$ so A, B are $I\alpha$ - compact sets over X but $A \cap B = \mathbb{N}$ which is not $I\alpha$ - compact set.

Remark 3.9 There is no relation between being the ideal topological space (X, τ, I) compact space or $I\alpha$ - compact space.

Example 3.10

- i. Consider the ideal topological space (X, τ, I) such that $X = \mathbb{N}, \tau = D$ and $I = \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N})$. Then $I\alpha O(X) = D$. We know that $\mathbb{N}$ is not compact space but the ideal topological space $(\mathbb{N}, D, I)$ is $I\alpha$ - compact space.
- ii. Consider the ideal topological space (X, τ, I) such that $X = \mathbb{N}, \tau = \{\mathbb{N}, \emptyset, \{1\}\}$ and $I = \{\emptyset\}$. Then $I\alpha O(X) = \{A \subseteq \mathbb{N}: 1 \in A\} \cup \{\emptyset\}$. We know that $\mathbb{N}$ is compact space but the ideal topological space $(\mathbb{N}, \tau, I)$ is not $I\alpha$ - compact space. Now, take $\{\{1, n\}: n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is an $I\alpha$ - open cover for $\mathbb{N}$, then there exists $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\cup \{1, m\}$ is finite subfamily of $\{1, n\}$ but $\mathbb{N} - \cup \{1, m\} \notin I$, and it is infinite. Hence $(\mathbb{N}, \tau, I)$ is not $I\alpha$ - compact space but $(\mathbb{N}, \tau)$ is compact.

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